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Bosh muharrir:

Z. Raxmanov – Nizomiy nomidagi O‘zbekiston Milliy Pedagogika Universiteti rektori v.v.b., iqtisodiyot fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD).

Mas’ul muharrir:

G. Ibragimova – Pedagogika-psixologiya va inklyuziv ta’lim fakulteti dekani, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Tahrir hay’ati:

N. Sh. Umarova – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor.

V. M. Karimova – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor.

Z. T. Nishanova – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor.

D. S. Karshiyeva – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor.

Nashrga tayyorlovchi:

R. Ashurov – psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

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EMOTIONAL BURNOUT AND STRESS AS PSYCHOLOGICAL RISKS OF A NOTARY’S PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

Arystanbek Aiymzhan

L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Doctoral Candidate.

Scientific Supervisor

Aitysheva Aigul Mukataevna

Candidate of Psychological Sciences,

Associate Professor, Senior Lecturer.

E-mail: u-a-17@mail.ru

Abstract: This study examines the psychological risks encountered by private notaries and employees of notarial offices, with particular attention to the impact of emotional burnout and stress in the course of professional notarial activity. The work of a notary is inherently multifaceted, characterized by a high degree of responsibility and intensive interaction with individuals from diverse social groups, which contributes to the emergence of emotional and occupational stress factors. Emotional burnout directly affects professional efficiency, decision-making, and communication with the public. The study proposes methods aimed at enhancing the psychological resilience of private notaries and reducing levels of emotional stress and professional burnout.

Key words: emotional burnout, stress, crisis situations, notarial activity, psychological risk.

Annotatsiya: This study examines the psychological risks encountered by private notaries and employees of notarial offices, with particular attention to the impact of emotional burnout and stress in the course of professional notarial activity. The work of a notary is inherently multifaceted, characterized by a high degree of responsibility and intensive interaction with individuals from diverse social groups, which contributes to the emergence of emotional and occupational stress factors. Emotional burnout directly affects professional efficiency, decision-making, and communication with the public. The study proposes methods aimed at enhancing the psychological resilience of private notaries and reducing levels of emotional stress and professional burnout.

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Аннотация: В настоящем исследовании рассматриваются психологические риски, с которыми сталкиваются частные нотариусы и сотрудники нотариальных контор, с особым вниманием к влиянию эмоционального выгорания и стресса в процессе профессиональной нотариальной деятельности. Труд нотариуса по своей природе многогранен, характеризуется высокой степенью ответственности и интенсивным взаимодействием с людьми из различных социальных групп, что способствует возникновению факторов эмоционального и профессионального стресса. Эмоциональное выгорание напрямую влияет на профессиональную эффективность, принятие решений и взаимодействие с общественностью. В исследовании предлагаются методы, направленные на повышение психологической устойчивости частных нотариусов и снижение уровня эмоционального стресса и профессионального выгорания.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональное выгорание, стресс, кризисные ситуации, нотариальная деятельность, психологический риск.

Currently, professionals in various fields face many stressful situations while doing their jobs. These come from a strong sense of responsibility for results, the need for professional communication, as well as conflicts and emotional stress in their interactions.

This phenomenon has not spared private notaries and employees of notarial offices in our country. Their professional work represents a socially important area that requires a high level of psychological resilience and emotional stability.

To comprehend individuals’ emotional and psychological states, to recognize indicators of manipulative behavior, to significantly reduce the risk of misjudgment, and to develop a clear algorithm of actions that enables the most accurate and effective identification of a person’s genuine intentions, legal education alone is insufficient [1, pp. 500–505].

Modern society, in accordance with the demands of the time, is in a state of constant transformation. Consequently, in order to perform their professional duties effectively—particularly to protect the rights and legitimate interests of individuals seeking notarial services—a notary must engage in continuous professional development and remain aligned with contemporary societal standards. Citizens turn to notaries daily with a wide range of legal issues requiring qualified assistance. A notary is not merely a legal expert; their professional competence extends beyond the boundaries of legal theory to encompass disciplines such as psychology, sociology, linguistics, and economics. By exercising the authority vested in them by the state, a notary assumes a profound level of social responsibility.

In the process of performing notarial actions related to vital and often complex (or conflictual) situations—such as inheritance cases, divorce proceedings, the drafting of wills, alimony payments, family disputes, enforcement inscriptions, powers of attorney, and property relations—it becomes evident that intricate psychological phenomena lie beneath the surface of legal norms and concepts.

Each individual behaves differently during the execution of notarial acts; therefore, the notary's manner of interaction also varies depending on the specific situation:

- Some individuals display self-confidence, perceiving notarial acts merely as a paid service, and in cases of dissatisfaction with the provided assistance, resort to threats of filing complaints.
- Others, on the contrary, experience considerable anxiety when visiting a notarial office.
- Certain clients place trust in the process and respond openly to all questions, whereas others fear the disclosure of their personal data.
- Some clients heed the notary's advice, striving to comprehend the nature and implications of the transaction, while others rely on the opinions of acquaintances and, conversely, challenge the notary's professional stance.

Conversely, some individuals seek to formalize fictitious, false, or fraudulent transactions, attempting to mislead the other party to the agreement, their attorneys, and, in some cases, even the notary, by employing various manipulative techniques that influence human consciousness, will, and behavior [1, pp. 500–505].

Regrettably, during education, internships, or professional development programs, notaries are not taught the theoretical foundations of psychology, linguistics, and other essential disciplines, nor are they offered courses aimed at the practical application of such knowledge.

Furthermore, although emotional burnout and professional stress among medical professionals, athletes, educators, lawyers, and social workers have been actively researched and reflected in numerous academic studies, data on emotional burnout and stress among notaries and employees of notarial offices—both in our country and abroad—remain extremely limited and virtually unexplored.

While the issue of professional stress in various fields of activity has been widely discussed at national events such as conferences and forums, and even though this topic has been analyzed in dissertation research and reflected in regulatory documents, comprehensive programs and frameworks aimed at systematically addressing it have not yet been developed. Moreover, there is a lack of up-to-date recommendations that take into account the latest achievements in psychological science (including behavioral approaches), neurobiology, and cognitive sciences [3, pp. 11–15].

The analysis of professional stress within legal professions, particularly in the notarial field, as well as the examination of this issue in a broader context, can make a significant contribution through the study of experiences and regulatory frameworks of countries where the problem has been identified and addressed at the level of professional legal communities [3, pp. 11–15].

How do emotional and professional burnout affect the quality of notarial practice?

Professional notarial activity possesses several specific features, many of which are influenced by adverse factors. This necessitates that specialists in the field have strong internal self-regulation resources, among which emotional stability constitutes a key component. The attainment of such stability is ensured through the application of methods and techniques of self-regulation [2, pp. 14–22].

The main risk factors influencing the development of emotional burnout syndrome are as follows:

- Professional factors (stereotypical perceptions of the profession, functional-role and regulatory-legal ambiguities, high responsibility for professional outcomes, among others);
- Professional and personal characteristics of the notary (insufficient training, as well as crisis and stress situations encountered in the course of professional and personal life).

The principal factors contributing to the development of professional stress syndrome include:

- Excessive workload in daily practice (in addition to performing notarial acts, this involves compiling notarial documents in both electronic and paper formats, maintaining accounting records, and carrying out other administrative tasks);

- Multifaceted nature of everyday professional activity (the necessity of maintaining a large number of interpersonal interactions with individuals seeking notarial services);
- Insufficient time for decision-making.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to reduce the level of emotional burnout and stress among private notaries and employees of notarial offices:

1. Promoting the role and social significance of notarial activity and increasing public awareness of the high level of responsibility borne by notaries through media outreach, seminars, and public events.
2. Introducing financial incentives for notaries, including tax benefits, access to professional office spaces, and the development of adequate infrastructure.
3. Organizing psychological training programs within professional development courses aimed at reducing occupational stress and emotional burnout (e.g., stress management, emotional intelligence, and meditation).
4. Implementing exercises and methodologies that foster emotional resilience and stability in the process of professional decision-making.

Thus, it can be emphasized that emotional and professional burnout are significant factors influencing the notary's professional activity.

First, the likelihood of errors in the decision-making process increases. Under stress, a notary may become unable to process information fully and accurately, which can result in mistakes during document verification or in the misjudgment of the parties' intentions.

Second, prolonged emotional and professional stress reduces endurance, which in turn leads to a loss of patience in communication with clients, the occurrence of serious errors, and the emergence of conflict situations.

Third, excessive emotional strain negatively affects cognitive functions, diminishing concentration and memory capacity. As a result, the effective performance of professional duties becomes increasingly difficult.

Moreover, stress and emotional exhaustion may undermine clients' trust, as the notary's unstable emotional state diminishes their professional credibility.

In conclusion, emotional and professional burnout exert a detrimental effect on the quality of notarial activity, increasing the likelihood of professional errors and legal risks.

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